

Data Walk #1: Brussels

Route and numbered list of data points

- 1. Place Rogier**
 - a) cameras
 - b) public wifi
 - c) view Proximus HQ
- 2. Metro**
 - a) cameras
 - b) public wifi
 - c) RFID access
- 3. City 2**
 - a) cameras
 - b) wifi/bluetooth tracking
- 4. Nieuwstraat**
 - a) cameras
 - b) smart bins
 - c) Fix My Street
 - d) wifi/bluetooth tracking
- 5. Muntplein**
 - a) ANPR cameras Parking
 - b) Green Parking dashboard
- 6. Muntpunt**

Note taking hints

1. Use the participants numbers and numbered list above for quick reference
E.g. "4 likes 2a" means "Participant 4 likes cameras in the metro."
2. Common types of data collection:
 - CAM = camera
 - BTT = bluetooth tracker
 - WFT = wifi tracker
 - RFID = RFID reader (e.g. metro gates)